

MORPHOPHYSIOLOGICAL ADAPTATION OF SOYBEAN (*GLYCINE MAX L.*) GENOTYPES UNDER SALINE CONDITIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14440763>

Abstract. *This study investigates the morphophysiological adaptability of soybean (*Glycine max L.*) genotypes under saline conditions. Ten soybean genotypes and the Selekt-302 variety were analyzed under laboratory conditions with 100 mM NaCl to assess their physiological responses. The total water content in leaves and transpiration rates of soybean genotypes significantly decreased under saline stress. Calculating the adaptability coefficient revealed that Gen-32 and Gen-31 exhibited the highest salt tolerance.*

Keywords: *salinity stress, Soybean (*Glycine max L.*), adaptability, total water content, transpiration rate, adaptability coefficient, variety, stress physiology, genotypes.*

Introduction

Soybean (*Glycine max L.*) is one of the most important crops globally, widely used in food, feed, and industrial products. In the arid and saline soil regions of Uzbekistan, growing soybean varieties adapted to complex ecological conditions is essential. Salinity stress is a critical environmental factor that adversely affects soybean growth, development, and yield.

The salt tolerance of plants varies among genotypes, making it crucial to study the physiological characteristics of selected genotypes to determine their adaptability to specific environmental conditions. Processes like maintaining water balance under saline conditions are vital in understanding the mechanisms of adaptability.

This study aimed to analyze the changes in physiological parameters, such as total water content and transpiration rates in leaves, under saline conditions in soybean genotypes and identify traits of salinity tolerance.

Literature Review

As the global population continues to grow, the demand for food supplies is increasing [9]. Soybean (*Glycine max L.*) is one of the most important leguminous crops, ranking fourth in terms of production worldwide [2, 6]. It provides essential nutritional components such as milk, protein, and oil, and is widely used for industrial purposes [1, 9]. Over time, the demand for soybeans has steadily increased. Abiotic stresses have negative effects on the growth and development of crops worldwide. Among these, soybean growth and yield are primarily affected by various ecological stress factors [8]. Salinity stress is a major environmental factor that severely impacts soybean growth, yield, and quality. It affects plants at all stages of their growth cycle [7, 11].

Data shows that approximately 19.5% of the world's agricultural lands are affected by salinity. In Uzbekistan, 53% of irrigated lands consist of saline soils. Soybeans are generally considered more susceptible to salinity stress than many other crops [2]. Soil salinization negatively affects various physiological activities in plants. It exacerbates oxidative damage,

reduces turgor pressure, and alters gas exchange in leaves, all of which hinder plant growth and development [4, 5, 10].

Salinity alters plant morphology, physiology, and metabolism, leading to a decrease in essential elements like phosphorus and calcium, as well as disrupting protein synthesis [3].

From this perspective, studying the response of soybean varieties and genotypes to salinity stress is a key area of interest.

Materials and Methods

In this study, experiments were conducted under greenhouse conditions using distilled water (optimal conditions) and water with 100 mM NaCl concentration (saline conditions). Ten soybean genotypes from the collection and the foreign Selekt-302 variety were analyzed.

During a 30-day period, the following parameters were measured for soybean plants under optimal and saline conditions: Total water content in leaves [13], Transpiration rates [12].

The adaptability coefficient ($K_{ad}\%$) was calculated to evaluate the sensitivity of physiological parameters to salinity stress using the formula by S.A. Eberhart and W.A. Russel:

$$K_{ad}\% = \left(\frac{x_1}{x_2} * 100 \right) - 100\%$$

where x_1 is the parameter value under optimal conditions, and x_2 is the parameter value under saline conditions.

Results

Salinity conditions significantly affected the total water content in the leaves and the transpiration rate of soybean varieties. The results of the study show that both parameters decreased under saline conditions, which is related to the physiological responses of the plants to stress.

Under saline conditions, the total water content in the leaves decreased in all varieties. This reduction might be associated with an increase in osmotic pressure in the leaves and a decreased ability to retain water due to salt stress. For example, in the variety Gen-37, the water content decreased by -10.7%, while in Gen-32, the reduction was only -3.0%. Varieties like Selekt-302 and Gen-8 also showed good results in terms of adaptability coefficients (-5.3% and -5.2%, respectively).

The significant reduction in water content under salinity stress indicates that the plants are attempting to limit water loss. At the same time, the relatively higher adaptability of varieties like Gen-32 and Gen-18 demonstrates their tolerance to salt stress.

A decrease in transpiration rate under saline conditions was observed as a response aimed at minimizing water loss. The largest reductions were recorded in Gen-15 (-46.6%) and Gen-11 (-41.6%).

These varieties responded quickly by closing their stomata, but this could potentially lead to a reduction in the photosynthesis process under salt stress conditions. On the other hand, the decrease in transpiration rate was minimal in Gen-31 and Gen-17 varieties (-0.7% and -5.2%, respectively), indicating their tolerance to salinity (table-1).

A decrease in transpiration rate under saline conditions indicates a reduction in the metabolic activity of plants under stress. This process is a crucial strategy for conserving water under saline conditions.

During the study, the adaptability coefficient was calculated as an indicator of salinity tolerance. This coefficient served as an essential tool to determine the ability of the varieties to adapt to salt stress.

The most adaptable varieties, Gen-32 and Gen-31, stood out with high adaptability coefficients, demonstrating their potential for selection and the creation of salt-tolerant varieties.

The salt-sensitive varieties, Gen-15 and Gen-11, were the most affected by salt stress, indicating their low tolerance to salinity.

Table 1. Total Water Content in Leaves and Transpiration Rate of Soybean Varieties and Lines under Control and Saline (NaCl) Conditions

№	Soybean lines and varieties	Total water content in leaves			Transpiration rate		
		Optimal conditions	Saline conditions	Kad%	Optimal conditions	Saline conditions	Kad%
		mean±SE	mean±SE		mean±SE	mean±SE	
1	Selekta-302	80,0±1,8	75,8±1,1	-5,3	276,0±9,7	261,5±5,9	-5,3
2	Gen-8	82,0±0,7	77,7±1,9	-5,2	290,3±5,5	211,7±10,5	-27,1
3	Gen-11	82,7±0,8	76,9±0,8	-7,0	434,1±8,2	253,7±5,7	-41,6
4	Gen-15	83,6±1,4	76,1±1,4	-9,0	516,2±12,1	275,4±9,5	-46,6
5	Gen-17	82,9±0,9	78,0±0,9	-5,9	329,8±5,1	312,7±6,5	-5,2
6	Gen-18	80,9±1,0	78,0±1,0	-3,6	350,0±7,6	268,8±13,6	-23,2
7	Gen-30	74,9±0,5	71,8±0,5	-4,1	201,4±13,1	136,1±10,3	-32,4
8	Gen-31	82,1±1,1	77,7±1,1	-5,4	364,9±12,7	362,2±9,3	-0,7
9	Gen-32	82,4±1,2	79,9±1,2	-3,0	349,9±16,6	326,9±14,9	-6,6
10	Gen-37	83,8±2,2	74,8±2,2	-10,7	229,4±15,7	213,9±12,5	-6,8
11	Green grain	80,9±0,8	77,5±0,8	-4,2	349,0±17,7	217,9±15,0	-37,6

The research findings provide a significant scientific basis for selecting soybean varieties to be grown under saline conditions. The salinity tolerance indicators can play an important role in the selection process. Specifically, Gen-32 and Gen-31 are recommended as salt-tolerant genotypes. Studying the genetic and physiological characteristics of varieties with low tolerance (e.g., Gen-15 and Gen-11) may help improve salinity tolerance in future breeding efforts.

Discussion. The findings reveal that salinity stress exerts a pronounced impact on the physiological processes of soybean plants, particularly on water retention and transpiration. The significant decrease in total water content and transpiration rates observed under saline conditions suggests that these parameters are vital indicators of salt stress response in soybean genotypes.

The adaptability coefficient provided valuable insights into the tolerance levels of various genotypes. Gen-32 and Gen-31 demonstrated superior adaptability, indicating their potential for cultivation in saline soils and use in breeding programs targeting salt-tolerant varieties. On the other hand, Gen-15 and Gen-11 were highly sensitive, showing substantial reductions in both parameters. Further investigation into the genetic and molecular bases of salt tolerance in these genotypes could enhance breeding strategies.

Moreover, the ability of salt-tolerant genotypes to maintain water content and regulate transpiration suggests their potential to mitigate the effects of salinity stress by optimizing osmotic adjustments and stomatal behavior. Future research employing molecular-genetic tools can help

unravel the underlying mechanisms and contribute to the development of resilient soybean cultivars.

Conclusion. This study highlights the impact of salinity stress on the water retention and transpiration processes in soybean genotypes. Identifying salt-tolerant varieties and incorporating them into breeding programs is a promising strategy for improving yields in saline-affected areas. Further molecular and genetic research is recommended to explore the adaptation mechanisms of these genotypes and enhance soybean resilience to abiotic stress.

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